

Clinical, physical, physiological, and cardiovascular risk patterns of adults with schizophrenia:

CORTEX-SP study.

Running title: Characterization of adults with schizophrenia

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Abstract

Schizophrenia (SP) is a severe mental illness with high rates of premature morbidity and mortality, associated with an unhealthy lifestyle and the side effects of drug treatment. The aim of the study were 1) to determine some key physical, physiological and biochemical markers of health status, including sleep quality, in adults (42 ± 10 yr) with SP ($n=126$) before starting a non-pharmacological therapeutic strategy, 2) to estimate cardiovascular risk (CVR) through different methods, and 3) to compare all studied variables with a HEALTHY population ($n=30$). Assessment was based on body composition, blood pressure with 24-hour ambulatory monitor, cardiorespiratory condition, quality of sleep with triaxial accelerometry for eight days and biochemical analysis. Participants with SP showed a cardiovascular risk profile including “overweight metabolically abnormal (outside optimal concentration of C-reactive protein >3 , high-density lipoprotein cholesterol $=40.0\pm 15.0$ mg/dL, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol >100 mg/dL, atherogenic index >3.5 , and uric acid $=6.0\pm 1.3$ mg/dL), low cardiorespiratory fitness (22.5 ± 9.0 mL \cdot kg $^{-1}\cdot$ min $^{-1}$) and ventilatory efficiency (POC $=30\pm 6$). Although individuals with SP slept more ($P<0.001$, $\Delta=33.3\%$) compared to HEALTHY, similar sleep efficiency ($>85\%$) showed both groups, but with higher ($P=0.004$, $\Delta=50.7\%$) levels of wake after sleep onset by SP. The assessment of CVR showed higher values ($P<0.05$) in SP (moderate risk) compared to HEALTHY (low risk) regardless the estimation system. The identification of specific clinical, physical and physiological CVR profile in SP illness compared to healthy people strongly suggest that targeting a comprehensive approach including non-pharmacological interventions.

Introduction

Schizophrenia (SP) is a chronic severe mental illness caused by a combination of genetic and external factors affecting 1% of people worldwide (Lieberman, Stroup, & Perkins, 2006). Individuals with SP are diagnosed at an early age, frequently follows a chronic course (Lieberman & First, 2018), and present a shorter life expectancy (*i.e.*, ~28.5 years less) than the general population (Olfson, Gerhard, Huang, Crystal, & Stroup, 2015). The higher mortality rate in SP (Laursen, Munk-Olsen, & Vestergaard, 2012) is not only caused by increased suicide but also associated with physical illness, being cardiovascular disease (CVD) the most common one (Olfson et al., 2015).

An unhealthy lifestyle, including lack of physical activity (PA) (Stubbs et al., 2016), smoking, abuse of alcohol or caffeine, poor diet (Ratliff et al., 2012), along with adverse effects of medications (Mukundan, Faulkner, Cohn, & Remington, 2010), and social and economic factors (*e.g.*, access to health care) (Correll et al., 2014) have an important bearing on the presence of cardiovascular risk (CVR) factors, such as high blood pressure (BP), elevated waist circumference, dyslipidemia, and glucose dysregulation (Ratliff et al., 2012).

Therefore, control and assessment of CVR in SP patients are recommended according to different clinical guidelines (American Diabetes Association, American Psychiatric Association, American Association of Clinical Endocrinologists, & North American Association for the Study of Obesity, 2004; De Hert et al., 2009; Saiz Ruiz et al., 2008). However, even though they appear to be cost-effective (Bruggeman, Schorr, Van der Elst, Postma, & Taxis, 2008; Gutierrez-Rojas et al., 2016), at this time they are not being implemented in the clinical care of patients (Mackin, Bishop, & Watkinson, 2007). Guidelines in people with SP include the need for comprehensive control of physical health monitorization, and recommend the control of PA levels, body mass gain through the waist-to-hip ratio and/or waist circumference, BP, use of tobacco and alcohol or other substances, dietary intake, fasting blood glucose level, fasting blood lipids, and prolactin levels (De Hert et al., 2009; National Collaborating Centre for Mental Health (UK), 2009). The risk factors should be managed according to the total CVD risk, and assessed by the score risk

charts such as Framingham Heart Study (FHS) and Systematic Coronary Risk Estimation (SCORE) system, which calculate risk according to age, smoking habit, sex, systolic BP (SBP) and total cholesterol (TC), or the ratio of total to high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) (De Hert et al., 2009; Piepoli et al., 2017). However, individuals with SP are typically younger, and more likely to be smokers compared to the populations used to derive traditional CVD risk scoring systems (Taxis, Schorr, Fouchier, Slooff, & Bruggeman, 2008). Therefore, the latest position statement from the European Psychiatric Association recommends the decision to include a relative risk chart for severe mental illness patients based on smoking habit, SBP, and TC (De Hert et al., 2009). In addition, and also based on the FHS method, the vascular age (VA) is another useful tool calculating the biological age of an individual's arteries (*i.e.*, the age of the vascular system of a person with different CVR factors) with the data on CVR factors (Cuende, Cuende, & Calaveras-Lagartos, 2010; Piepoli et al., 2017).

Besides traditional parameters, cardiorespiratory fitness (CRF; *i.e.*, the maximum amount of oxygen that can be taken in, transported to and utilized by the working muscle during exercise) (Hill & Hartley Lupton, 1923) is considered a vital sign and has emerged as a modifiable risk factor with the aim of attenuating the risk of developing non-communicable diseases (Despres, 2016; Kaminsky et al., 2019). Thus, the strong association between reduced CVR and higher levels of CRF, also inversely associated with CVD mortality, is common knowledge (Kaminsky et al., 2019). In this sense, early studies with SP have shown a 15% lower CRF values than healthy controls (Scheewe, Takken, Kahn, Cahn, & Backx, 2012).

Another parameter that plays an essential role in our physical and mental health, wellness and overall vitality is good sleep quality, including sleep continuity variables (*i.e.*, sleep latency, number of awakenings, wake after sleep onset [WASO], and sleep efficiency) (Ohayon et al., 2017). A consensus recommendation for the minimum amount of sleep duration to support optimal health in adults was set in 7 hours, with uncertainty regarding the appropriateness of >9 hours. Disrupted sleep is common in SP and is associated with symptom severity (Ashton & Jagannath, 2020). Traditional sedative-hypnotics and second-generation sedating antipsychotics

are the usual drugs prescribed for sleep stabilization (Ashton & Jagannath, 2020). However, when second-generation antipsychotics are taken by stable patients with SP, activating and sedating side effects, and body mass gain are presented, which could be associated with daily functionality (Tandon et al., 2020).

To the best of our knowledge, no reports are available that have carried out a clinical, physical, and physiological characterization of the SP population, including cardiovascular risk profile through different methods. Therefore, the main purposes of this study were: 1) to determine some key physical, physiological and biochemical markers of health status, including sleep quality, in adults with SP before starting a non-pharmacological therapeutic strategy, 2) to estimate CVR through different methods, and 3) to compare all studied variables with a healthy population.

Methods

Study participants

The CORTEX-SP study was conducted between May 2018 and July 2020 in Vitoria-Gasteiz (Basque Country, Spain). The current baseline study comprised a total of 126 participants (CORTEX) aged between 18 and 65 years (mean 41.6 ± 10.3 years), 105 men (83.3%), and 21 women (16.7%). All participants had a diagnosis of SP according to DSM-5 F20.9 (*Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition*), with a disease evolution time greater than two years, stable and at least moderate cognitive impairment in the MATRICS variables (T score <40 in at least one of the seven cognitive domains). The exclusion criteria were: clinically unstable patients (total PANSS-Positive score >19); cognitive impairment secondary to another disease (dementia, mental retardation); main diagnosis of substance use disorder or presenting active substance use at the time of the study; patients who have required relevant modifications of the antipsychotic drug treatment in the previous three months; patients doing another specific program of cognitive rehabilitation; patients with active major affective disorder; incompatibilities with the magnetic resonance imaging study (*i.e.*, claustrophobia, metal implants in the body, patients undergoing treatment by deep brain stimulation); secondary HTN; left

ventricular hypertrophy (estimated left ventricular mass up to 103 g/m² for men and up to 89 g/m² for women) (Lang et al., 2015); the presence of one severe or, uncontrolled CVR factor, or diabetes mellitus more than 10 years since diagnosis, or with associated organopathy; other significant medical conditions including but not limited to chronic or recurrent respiratory, gastrointestinal, or neuromuscular conditions; musculoskeletal problems interfering with exercise; autoimmune or collagen vascular diseases; immunodeficiency diseases or a positive HIV test; anemias, bleeding disorders, chronic thrombotic disorders, or hypercoagulable states; malignancies in the past 5 years, with the exception of skin cancer therapeutically controlled; any other medical condition or disease that is life-threatening or that can interfere with or be aggravated by exercise, pregnancy or breast-feeding and plans to be out of the city more than two weeks. The study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Basque Country (PI2017044), and written informed consent was obtained from all participants before any data collection (Clinical Trials.gov identifier, NCT03509597).

On the other hand, a HEALTHY sample (n=30, 40% men, and 60% women) was recruited from the community (approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of the Basque Country, UPV/EHU, M10/2018/229) and excluded if they had any chronic medical illness, were taking any daily prescription medications, had current medical symptoms, had abnormal findings on physical examination (including BP \geq 140/90 mmHg, or overweight \geq 25 kg/m²), or had abnormal results on the screening test (rest and exercise electrocardiogram).

Measurements

Stature and body mass were measured, and body mass index (BMI) was calculated as the total body mass divided by height squared (kg/m²). Waist and hip circumferences were taken, and waist to hip ratio (WHR) was defined as waist circumference divided by hip circumference both in centimeters. Moreover, the estimation of fat-free mass (FFM), total body water (TBW), and fat mass (FM) were made by bioelectrical impedance (Tanita, BF 350, Arlington Heights, IL, USA).

Blood pressure measurements were obtained using an ambulatory BP monitoring recorder (ABPM) (6100 and 7100, Welch Allyn, New York, NY, USA) for a whole day (24h), through

intervals of 30 minutes during the day and intervals of 60 minutes during the night. The variables considered from the ABPM measures were mean values of SBP, diastolic BP (DBP), and heart rate (HR).

Age, diabetes mellitus and cigarette smoking status were assessed by self-report. All medications prescribed to participants were recorded and classified in their group: aripiprazole, clozapine, paliperidone, olanzapine, quetiapine, haloperidol, risperidone, ziprasidone, levomepromazine, perphenazine, and lurasidone.

Physical fitness measurements included a symptom-limited cardiopulmonary exercise peak test (CPET) and the Modified Shuttle Walking Test (Bradley, Howard, Wallace, & Elborn, 1999). The CPET was performed on an electronically braked Lode Excalibur Sport Cycle Ergometer (Groningen, Netherlands) starting at 40W with a gradual increment of 10W each minute in ramp protocol. Expired gas was analyzed with a system (Ergo CardMedi-soft S.S, Belgium Ref. USM001 V1.0) that was calibrated before each test for the determination of peak oxygen consumption ($\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$), which was defined as the highest oxygen uptake value attained toward the end of the test. Achievement of $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$ was assumed with the presence of two or more of the following criteria: 1) volitional fatigue (>18 on Borg scale), 2) peak respiratory exchange ratio (RER) ≥ 1.1 , 3) achieving $>85\%$ of age-predicted maximum heart rate, and 4) failure of oxygen consumption ($\dot{V}O_2$) and/or heart rate to increase with further increases in work rate (Mezzani et al., 2012). In addition, the cardiorespiratory optimal point (COP) was assessed objectively. Thus, it considers the achievement of the COP at the nadir of the ventilation ratio (VE) ($L \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$) and VO_2 ($\text{mL} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$) obtained at every minute during the maximum CPET, the so-called ventilatory equivalent for VO_2 (VE/VO_2) (Ramos, Ricardo, & Araujo, 2012). First ventilatory threshold (VT_1) was identified as the point of transition in the carbon dioxide production (VCO_2) vs. VO_2 slope from less than 1 to greater than 1, or VT_1 was also identified as the nadir of the VE of VO_2 vs. work rate relationship (Mezzani et al., 2012).

A blood sample (12.5 mL) was collected from each participant in the Alava Psychiatric Hospital after an overnight fast to determine the biochemical profile including hemoglobin,

hematocrit, TC, HDL-C, LDL-C, TG, glucose, insulin, aspartate transaminase (AST), alanine transaminase (ALT), gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT), CRP, uric acid, creatinine, sodium, potassium, and albumin. HOMA-IR was used to evaluate insulin resistance [fasting serum insulin ($\mu\text{U/mL}$) \times fasting plasma glucose (mg/dL)/405] (Matthews et al., 1985).

Sleep quality analysis was objectively and continuously assessed through a triaxial accelerometer (ActiGraph GT3X+, Pensacola, Florida, USA). Participants always wore the accelerometer on their non-dominant wrist with a velcro strap for eight consecutive days (24-h), except during water-based activities, and no other device was implemented during this period (*e.g.*, ABMP). On the eighth day, the accelerometer was returned to the investigators. The sleep measures were calculated from raw ActiGraph data for each unit, they were downloaded, treated, and analyzed using the manufacturer's software (Actilife 6.11.9) with 60-s epoch length. The following sleep variables were derived from ActiGraph data: Total sleep time (TST) (min of sleep between sleep onset and wake time), WASO (total min awake once they fall asleep) and sleep efficiency, that is obtained from $[(\text{total sleep time}/\text{total sleep time}) \times 100]$, and values below 85% are generally considered indicative of clinically significant reduced sleep efficiency (Schutte-Rodin, Broch, Buysse, Dorsey, & Sateia, 2008). Sleep patterns were assessed using a previously validated software algorithm based on the Cole-Kripke scoring method (Cole, Kripke, Gruen, Mullaney, & Gillin, 1992) that analyzes the raw ActiGraph data to calculate sleep time.

The CVR profile was calculated with the FHS, SCORE, and a relative risk chart, which are quantitative methods used in primary care for assessment of the general CVR profile. In the FHS method, the sex-specific risk factors considered were: age, HDL-C, TC, SBP, diabetes mellitus and smoking status. Each variable received a weighted score, and the sum of the score for each variable was then translated to the risk for a cardiovascular event in 10 years. Thus, a score of 10% means that there is a 10% chance of having a cardiovascular event within the next 10 years, under 6% is considered low risk, between 6 and 20% is considered medium risk, and a score of at least 20% is considered high risk (D'Agostino RB et al., 2008). On the other hand, and applying the FHS method, the VA indicates the biological age of the individual's vascular system,

as the age a person would be with the same calculated CVR but whose risk factors were all within normal ranges. (D'Agostino RB et al., 2008). The SCORE charts were developed to estimate cardiovascular risk in European populations (adult men >40 years of age and women >50 years of age or post-menopausal) according to age, sex, smoking habit, SBP and TC. The risk categorization was: calculated SCORE <1% low risk, $\geq 1\%$ and <5% low- to moderate-risk, $\geq 5\%$ and <10% high-risk, and $\geq 10\%$ very high-risk (Graham et al., 2007; Piepoli et al., 2017). The relative risk chart, including in the European Guidelines on CVD prevention, was based on smoking habit, SBP and TC (De Hert et al., 2009; Piepoli et al., 2017).

Statistical analysis

All variables were deemed normally distributed using a Shapiro-Wilk apart from BMI, FFM, TBW, FBM, SBP, $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$, peak metabolic equivalent of task (MET_{peak}), $\dot{V}CO_{2peak}$, COP, workload, time, distance, DBP_{peak} , RER_{peak} , VT_1 , Modified Shuttle Walk Test, glucose, HOMA, insulin, HDL-C, TC/HDL-C ratio, TG, AST, ALT, GGT, creatine, sodium, potassium, CRP, VA, sleep efficiency, WASO and TST. Descriptive statistics were calculated for all variables. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) when normality is met and as median \pm interquartile range when is non-normal distribution. An independent samples t-test was used to determine whether there was a significant group difference for all parametric variables. In non-normal distribution variables, the Mann–Whitney U test was used to test differential between groups. Cohen's d was calculated to describe the standardized mean difference in between-group effect sizes. The effect sizes were interpreted as small ($d=0.2$), medium ($d=0.5$), and large ($d=0.8$) based on benchmarks suggested by Cohen (Cohen, 1998). The Chi-square test was used to test differences in categorical variables between groups and Cramer's V was calculated to describe the standardized mean difference between-group effect sizes. Cramer's V is between 0 and 1, when it is greater than 0.26 it is considered a significant correlation, 0.6 means relatively intense correlation and 1, a perfect relationship (McHugh, 2013). The Friedman test, a non-normal related test with data matrix segmentation, was used to calculate the differences between VA and

chronological age. Statistical significance was set at $P<0.05$. The statistical analyses were performed with the SPSS version 25.0 software package.

Results

Characteristics of the studied populations are shown in Table 1. Related to body composition, CORTEX showed higher ($P<0.001$) values in body mass ($\Delta=26.6\%$), BMI ($\Delta=21.6\%$), waist ($\Delta=29.2\%$), hip ($\Delta=8.2\%$), WHR ($\Delta=17.9\%$), and FBM ($\Delta=23.3\%$), but lower ($P<0.001$) values in FFM ($\Delta=-6.4\%$) and TBW ($\Delta=-6.4\%$) compared to HEALTHY. As a consequence, HEALTHY values are within normality, but not those in CORTEX, which are considered as CVR factors (BMI >25 kg/m² as overweight, FBM=26.5% as obesity, and waist circumference=96.5 cm as high metabolic risk) (US Department of Health and Human Services, 2013).

Both groups showed optimal BP values (*i.e.*, SBP <120 mmHg, DBP <80 mmHg) (Volpe, Gallo, Battistoni, & Tocci, 2019) with no differences ($P>0.05$) between groups. However, the mean heart rate was higher ($P<0.001$, $\Delta=39.1\%$) in CORTEX compared to HEALTHY, showing 23 beats more per minute. Approximately 63% of CORTEX participants reported currently smoking cigarettes, compared ($P<0.001$) with 16% in HEALTHY.

As for the medication-pharmacological therapy, HEALTHY did not take any regularly prescribed drug, while in CORTEX all received controlled, regular and mandatory antipsychotic medication therapy (Table 1).

When **exercise function** was assessed CORTEX showed lower values ($P<0.001$) of CRF (relative $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$, $\Delta=-55.0\%$; MET_{peak}, $\Delta=-54.9\%$), test duration ($\Delta=-44.4\%$), distance performed ($\Delta=-64.4\%$), peak workload ($\Delta=-45.9\%$), peak heart rate ($\Delta=-15.2\%$), VT₁ ($\Delta=-57.1\%$), and distance in MSWT ($\Delta=-47.0\%$) compared to HEALTHY (Table 2). According to Kaminsky et al. (Kaminsky, Imboden, Arena, & Myers, 2017), CORTEX participants were classified in the 20th percentile with a low physical condition ($\dot{V}O_{2peak}=22.5\pm 9.0$ mL·kg⁻¹·min⁻¹). Further, CORTEX showed higher values in the COP variable ($P<0.001$, $\Delta=20\%$), compared to HEALTHY, showing

a lower ventilatory capacity (Ramos et al., 2012), and DBP_{peak} ($P=0.034$, $\Delta=10.4\%$). No significant differences were shown when comparing the SBP_{peak} and RER_{peak} values between groups (Table 2).

Regarding **biochemical profile** characteristics (Table 3) CORTEX participants showed upper optimal concentration of LDL-C (>100 mg/dL), atherogenic index (i.e., $TC/HDL-C > 3.5$) (National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP) Expert Panel on Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Cholesterol in Adults (Adult Treatment Panel III), Circulation 2002), CRP, a proinflammatory biomarker which is considered cardiometabolically unhealthy in values >3 mg/L (Hamer & Stamatakis, 2012), and borderline-serum uric acid concentration (6.0 ± 1.3 mg/dL) (Johnson, 2015) and HDL-C (40.0 ± 15.0 mg/dL). On the other hand, both groups (i.e., CORTEX and HEALTHY) presented normal concentrations for TC (<200 mg/dL), TG (<200 mg/dL) (National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP) Expert Panel on Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Cholesterol in Adults (Adult Treatment Panel III), Circulation 2002), fasting plasma glucose (<100 mg/dL) and insulin (<16.7 μ U/mL) concentrations, HOMA-IR (<3.8) (Alberti, Zimmet, & Shaw, 2006), and the three hepatic enzymes (AST >30 U/L, ALT >30 U/L, GGT >50 U/L) (Nagano, Sasaki, & Kumagai, 2010). After comparing both groups, CORTEX showed higher ($P < 0.05$) values in hemoglobin (mean difference, MD=0.5; 95% confidence interval, CI=0.0, 1.0 mg/dL), glucose (MD=13.1; 95% CI=3.3, 22.8 mg/dL), HOMA-IR (MD=2.5; 95% CI= 1.2, 3.7), insulin (MD=8.5; 95% CI=5.3, 11.7 μ U/mL), TC/HDL-C ratio (MD=1.8; 95% CI=1.4, 2.1), TG (MD=77.4; 95% CI=57.2, 97.5 mg/dL), ALT (MD=6.7; 95% CI=3.4, 10.1 U/L), GGT (MD=9.3; 95% CI=0.6, 17.9 U/L), uric acid (MD=1.2; 95% CI=0.7, 1.8 mg/dL), and CRP (MD=5.1; 95% CI=3.1, 7.1 mg/L) compared to HEALTHY. Moreover, HDL-C (MD=-21.5; 95% CI=-26.1, 17.0 mg/dL) and AST (MD=-2.6; 95% CI=-5.3, 0.0 mg/dL) concentrations were lower in CORTEX than in HEALTHY group.

The analysis of sleep quality from actigraphy (Table 4) showed higher TST ($P < 0.001$, $\Delta=33.3\%$) and WASO ($P=0.004$, $\Delta=50.7\%$) in CORTEX compared to HEALTHY. However, when sleep efficiency (i.e., the relationship between sleeping time and bed time) was analyzed no

significant differences ($P=0.987$) between groups were found, with both exceeding 85%, which is considered optimal sleep efficiency.

The CVR assessment (Figure 1) showed differences ($P<0.001$) between groups with higher values in CORTEX compared to HEALTHY (FHS, MD=5.7, 95% CI=4.0, 7.5%; SCORE, MD=0.4, 95% CI=0.2, 0.7%; and relative risk chart, MD=1.0, 95% CI=0.7, 1.3%). Thus, in accordance with the ACC/AHA Guidelines on the assessment of CVR (D'Agostino RB et al., 2008) and European Guidelines on CVD prevention (Piepoli et al., 2017), considering SCORE both groups were classified as low risk, but taking into account FHS and relative chart, CORTEX was considered to have moderate risk, while HEALTHY low risk. When VA was analyzed (Figure 2): 1) CORTEX showed higher ($P<0.001$) values than HEALTHY (MD=15.4, 95% CI=-9.5, 21.3 years) and higher ($P<0.001$) values than their chronological age (MD=7.6, 95% CI=5.6, 9.5 years), and 2) VA in HEALTHY was lower ($P<0.001$) than their chronological age (MD=-6.5, 95% CI=-9.6, 3.4 years).

Discussion

In the present study, an analysis of physical, physiological and biochemical markers of the health status in people with SP (*i.e.*, CORTEX sample) was carried out and compared to a HEALTHY population sample. The main findings of this study were: 1) CORTEX showed a worse physical, physiological and biochemical profile than HEALTHY with overweight/obesity; upper optimal LDL-C, atherogenic index, CRP and uric acid concentration; low CRF, ventilatory capacity and HDL-C concentrations, and high mean heart rate, 2) both groups showed similar optimal sleep efficiency, but population with SP sleep more time and also spend more time awake once they fall sleep than HEALTHY, and 3) CVR was significantly higher in CORTEX than in HEALTHY regardless the scoring system. These findings highlight the importance of CVR assessment of people with SP for the prevention of CVD in clinical practice.

Cardiometabolic diseases and SP disorder share overlapping genetic backgrounds leading to higher CVR predisposition (Lis, Stanczykiewicz, Liskiewicz, & Misiak, 2020), and chronic inflammation (Fond, Lancon, Korchia, Auquier, & Boyer, 2020). On the other hand, for SP

disorder, there is, nowadays, a prevailing use of second-generation over first-generation antipsychotics leading a shift in the adverse effects (*i.e.*, from extrapyramidal to metabolic abnormalities) (Maayan, Vakhrusheva, & Correll, 2010). Thus, previous studies have shown that early in the psychotic illness and after a few weeks of antipsychotic exposure, lifetime-related metabolic abnormalities are identified (Correll et al., 2014). Likewise, stable patients with SP taking second-generation antipsychotics are living with many side effects including body mass gain (Tandon et al., 2020) and dyslipidemia (Huang, T. L. & Chen, 2005). In this sense, there is some growing of evidence now that second-generation antipsychotics induce significantly appetite increase related to the impaired hormonal activity of adipose tissue (*i.e.*, dysregulation in adiponectin, leptin, resistin and visfatin hormones) leading to lipid profile disturbances (Huang, J. et al., 2020; Lis et al., 2020). In the present study, ~94% of SP participants were treated with atypical called second-generation antipsychotics drugs (Table 1), and corroborate what is presented in the aforementioned scientific literature. They showed a clear profile of increased cigarette smoking, overweight (>25 kg/m²), obesity (FBM=26.5%), high metabolic risk based on waist circumference values (>88 cm in women and >102 cm in men) (ACSM, 2018) and several metabolic risk indices (dyslipidemia with high LDL-C and atherogenic index, and low HDL-C concentrations; systemic inflammation with high CRP level; and hyperuricemia) compared with similarly aged HEALTHY sample. As a result, although the SP population of this study presented some favorable metabolic features such as glycemic profile, TG, and hepatic enzymes, the other cardiometabolic risk factors lead to categorizing the sample as “*overweight metabolically abnormal*” according to Wildman modified criteria (Martinez-Larrad et al., 2014). Adding to the aforementioned picture, in the present study, resting heart rate values are 39.1% higher in the CORTEX (81±11 bpm) than the HEALTHY (58±7 bpm) population (Table 1). This result confirms the autonomic dysregulation in SP with parasympathetic hypoactivity accompanied by relative sympathetic dominance (Iwamoto et al., 2012a; Montaquila, Trachik, & Bedwell, 2015). It seems that antipsychotic drugs exert a significant dose-dependent effect on autonomic nervous system activity leading to a sympathovagal imbalance and that optimal antipsychotic dose is required to avoid possible CVD adverse events (Iwamoto et al., 2012b). Hence, a coordinated set

of actions to eliminate or minimize the CVR factors and the impact on CVD should be the aim in this specific as in the general population (Piepoli et al., 2017).

Adding to that, a previous meta-analysis has confirmed that people with SP engage in less moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (*i.e.*, the key determinant to produced biological adaptations to increase CRF) compared to healthy controls (Stubbs et al., 2016). Therefore, in the current study the low physical condition (Kaminsky et al., 2017) presented by CORTEX compared (-55%, $P < 0.001$, d Cohen=2.59) to HEALTHY ($\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$: 22.5 ± 9.0 vs. 50.0 ± 12.0 mL·kg⁻¹·min⁻¹; MET_{peak}: 6.4 ± 2.7 vs. 14.2 ± 3.2), in combination with the high COP (*i.e.*, ventilatory inefficiency >30) might be predictors of all-cause mortality (Ramos & Araujo, 2017). Thus, the trilogy of “*overweight metabolically abnormal, low CRF and high COP*” confirms a powerful CVR profile in the studied SP population. Different factors could justify the aforementioned disparities: negative symptoms, depression, lack of access to infrastructure or facilities, poverty, low self-efficacy in exercise, limited knowledge of the benefits of physical activity, facilitating processes limited and general risk behaviors (Bassilios, Judd, Pattison, Nicholas, & Moeller-Saxone, 2015). Further, in the present investigation, it is important to mention the likely effects of other concomitant medications apart of antipsychotics, such as mood stabilizers (~50% of participants) or antidepressants (27%) to increase the sedentary behavior and/or lack of physical activity.

On the other hand, literature often presents the SP population to suffer from primary hypertension (Tumiel, Wichniak, Jarema, & Lew-Starowicz, 2019). Nonetheless, the findings of the present study show normal BP values (115/70 mmHg) in CORTEX, with no significant difference to HEALTHY (113/68 mmHg). It has been shown that longer antipsychotic treatment is associated with lower SBP due to α -adrenergic blockade (Correll et al., 2014). Previous studies have shown that clozapine (Parks, Parks, Yost, Bennett, & Onwuameze, 2018) and olanzapine (Choure, Gosavi, & Nanotkar, 2014) significantly reduced SBP and was associated with hypotension (note that 43.0% and 21.1% of our participants were taken clozapine and olanzapine, respectively).

It has been confirmed that poor sleep is associated with a wide range of impaired psychological and physical well-being in the SP population (Fond et al., 2020). Although previous researches indicate that each person should sleep depending on individual needs, it is generally concluded that the appropriate sleep pattern has to be the intermediate one (*i.e.*, an average of 7-9 hours) to find a positive association between sleep duration and general health (Watson et al., 2015). In the present study, it was noteworthy that while CORTEX showed a daily average sleep duration of 554 minutes (*i.e.*, 9.2 h), HEALTHY, by contrast, presented significantly lower duration (*i.e.*, 415 min=6.9 h). There are no experimental data to suggest a causal role for long sleep duration in relation to mental health, and there is also no clear evidence for increased risk of CVD and hypertension for sleep duration >8 hours (Watson et al., 2015). In this sense, sleepiness/sedation is one of the main side effects of taking second-generation antipsychotics (Tandon et al., 2020), and also one of the most prevalent reported secondary effects for discontinuation in the case of ziprasidone and haloperidol (Gómez-Revuelta et al., 2020). On the other hand, according to the general recommendations of the National Sleep Foundation, the main indicators for good sleep quality are sleep efficiency and WASO (Ohayon et al., 2017). In the current investigation, both groups showed a very good sleep efficiency >85% (*i.e.*, the relationship between TST and bedtime) (Schutte-Rodin et al., 2008); however, when WASO was analyzed significant differences were observed with higher values for CORTEX compared to HEALTHY (50±28 vs. 33±13 min, $\Delta=51\%$). In this sense, knowing that a WASO \geq 41 minutes does not indicate good sleep quality (Ohayon et al., 2017), this could be questioned in the SP studied population. The scientific evidence strongly suggests that disrupted sleep and dysfunctional circadian rhythm is a common feature of SP disorder with alterations in dopamine signaling to be central to this role (Ashton & Jagannath, 2020). Further, there is also evidence that antipsychotics affect the circadian system, demonstrating the importance of appropriate timing of drug administration to prevent further sleep and circadian disturbance (Ashton & Jagannath, 2020).

Taking into account altogether, it seems essential a rapidly and accuracy of CVR assessment through different systematic screening (Piepoli et al., 2017). In the present study, regardless the CVR estimation model, CORTEX showed significantly higher CVR profile compared to HEALTHY (Figure 1 & 2). Thus, with regard to 10-year coronary risk through FHS, CORTEX presented with moderate CVR (8.4%), while HEALTHY low risk (2.7%). These results in the SP population were similar to those found in previous research (Gutierrez-Rojas et al., 2016). Further, the SCORE data indicated that the total CV event risk, although significantly different, is low for the both studied groups. However, as noted in the introduction, SCORE is designed for people >50 years, and a low absolute risk may be masking a higher relative risk. Therefore, when the relative risk chart based on smoking habit, SBP and TC (De Hert et al., 2009) was used, CORTEX was classified from low-to-moderate risk (2%) and HEALTHY low risk (1%). Accordingly, VA was significantly higher ($P<0.001$) than chronological age in CORTEX (48 vs. 42 years) and lower ($P<0.001$) in HEALTHY group (36 vs. 40.0 years). In this way, the age of the vascular system in CORTEX was “older”, but “younger” in HEALTHY (Figure 2). Thus, the presentation of VA to the patient could be a useful tool in communicating about CVR, being able to understand the particular risk means in terms of life (Cuende et al., 2010).

Taking together, these findings highlight the view and counseling to offer a healthy lifestyle (*i.e.*, physical activity, healthy diet and toxic substances control) for reducing CVR and prevent CVD. Thus, next step could be to develop a more personalized approach in both pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatment.

Although the present study has highlighted the significant differences in a population with SP compared to similarly aged HEALTHY people according to physical, physiological, and biochemical characteristics, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, although the sample size could be sufficient as an initial investigation, it would not be comparable with that of larger epidemiological studies. Secondly, the current study only presented 17% of women in the SP studied population, which does not represent an equal gender split of the sample, and it has been the main reason for not analyzing differences by sex. However, taking into account the

difficulties involved in recruiting volunteers with mental disfunction, it could argue that the sample is adequate.

Conclusion

In closing, the identification of specific clinical, physical and physiological CVR profile in SP illness compared to healthy people strongly suggest that targeting a comprehensive approach including non-pharmacological interventions, such as physical exercise and/or cognitive rehabilitation, could be effective and beneficial in the evolution of the disease.

Author's contribution

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References

ACSM. (2018). *Guidelines for exercise testing and prescription* (10th Edition ed.) American College of Sports Medicine.

- Alberti, K. G., Zimmet, P., & Shaw, J. (2006). Metabolic syndrome--a new world-wide definition. A consensus statement from the international diabetes federation. *Diabetic Medicine : A Journal of the British Diabetic Association*, 23(5), 469-480. doi:DME1858 [pii]
- American Diabetes Association, American Psychiatric Association, American Association of Clinical Endocrinologists, & North American Association for the Study of Obesity. (2004). Consensus development conference on antipsychotic drugs and obesity and diabetes. *Diabetes Care*, 27(2), 596-601. doi:10.2337/diacare.27.2.596 [doi]
- Ashton, A., & Jagannath, A. (2020). Disrupted sleep and circadian rhythms in schizophrenia and their interaction with dopamine signaling. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 14, 636. doi:10.3389/fnins.2020.00636 [doi]
- Bassilios, B., Judd, F., Pattison, P., Nicholas, A., & Moeller-Saxone, K. (2015). Predictors of exercise in individuals with schizophrenia: A test of the transtheoretical model of behavior change. *Clinical Schizophrenia & Related Psychoses*, 8(4), 173-82, 182A. doi:10.3371/CSRP.BAJU.030113 [doi]
- Bradley, J., Howard, J., Wallace, E., & Elborn, S. (1999). Validity of a modified shuttle test in adult cystic fibrosis. *Thorax*, 54(5), 437-439. doi:10.1136/thx.54.5.437 [doi]
- Bruggeman, R., Schorr, S., Van der Elst, K., Postma, M., & Taxis, K. (2008). Cost-effectiveness of screening for diabetes in a cohort of patients with schizophrenia. *Schizophrenia Research*, 102(1), 161-162.
- Choure, B. K., Gosavi, D., & Nanotkar, S. (2014). Comparative cardiovascular safety of risperidone and olanzapine, based on electrocardiographic parameters and blood pressure: A prospective open label observational study. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology*, 46(5), 493-497. doi:10.4103/0253-7613.140579 [doi]

- Cohen, J. (1998). Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences.
- Cole, R. J., Kripke, D. F., Gruen, W., Mullaney, D. J., & Gillin, J. C. (1992). Automatic sleep/wake identification from wrist activity. *Sleep, 15*(5), 461-469.
doi:10.1093/sleep/15.5.461 [doi]
- Correll, C. U., Robinson, D. G., Schooler, N. R., Brunette, M. F., Mueser, K. T., Rosenheck, R. A., . . . Kane, J. M. (2014). Cardiometabolic risk in patients with first-episode schizophrenia spectrum disorders: Baseline results from the RAISE-ETP study. *JAMA Psychiatry, 71*(12), 1350-1363. doi:10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2014.1314 [doi]
- Cuende, J. I., Cuende, N., & Calaveras-Lagartos, J. (2010). How to calculate vascular age with the SCORE project scales: A new method of cardiovascular risk evaluation. *European Heart Journal, 31*(19), 2351-2358. doi:10.1093/eurheartj/ehq205 [doi]
- D'Agostino RB, S., Vasan, R. S., Pencina, M. J., Wolf, P. A., Cobain, M., Massaro, J. M., & Kannel, W. B. (2008). General cardiovascular risk profile for use in primary care: The framingham heart study. *Circulation, 117*(6), 743-753.
doi:10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.107.699579 [doi]
- De Hert, M., Dekker, J. M., Wood, D., Kahl, K. G., Holt, R. I., & Moller, H. J. (2009). Cardiovascular disease and diabetes in people with severe mental illness position statement from the european psychiatric association (EPA), supported by the european association for the study of diabetes (EASD) and the european society of cardiology (ESC). *European Psychiatry : The Journal of the Association of European Psychiatrists, 24*(6), 412-424.
doi:10.1016/j.eurpsy.2009.01.005 [doi]
- Despres, J. P. (2016). Physical activity, sedentary behaviours, and cardiovascular health: When will cardiorespiratory fitness become a vital sign? *The Canadian Journal of Cardiology, 32*(4), 505-513. doi:10.1016/j.cjca.2015.12.006 [doi]

Fond, G., Lancon, C., Korchia, T., Auquier, P., & Boyer, L. (2020). The role of inflammation in the treatment of schizophrenia. *Frontiers in Psychiatry, 11*, 160.

doi:10.3389/fpsyt.2020.00160 [doi]

Gómez-Revuelta, M., Pelayo-Terán, J. M., Juncal-Ruiz, M., Vázquez-Bourgon, J., Suárez-Pinilla, P., Romero-Jiménez, R., . . . Crespo-Facorro, B. (2020). Antipsychotic treatment effectiveness in first episode of psychosis: PAFIP 3-year follow-up randomized clinical trials comparing haloperidol, olanzapine, risperidone, aripiprazole, quetiapine, and ziprasidone. *Int J Neuropsychopharmacol, 23*(4), 217-229.

Graham, I., Atar, D., Borch-Johnsen, K., Boysen, G., Burell, G., Cifkova, R., . . . European Heart Network (EHN). (2007). European guidelines on cardiovascular disease prevention in clinical practice: Executive summary. fourth joint task force of the european society of cardiology and other societies on cardiovascular disease prevention in clinical practice (constituted by representatives of nine societies and by invited experts). *European Journal of Cardiovascular Prevention and Rehabilitation : Official Journal of the European Society of Cardiology, Working Groups on Epidemiology & Prevention and Cardiac Rehabilitation and Exercise Physiology, 14 Suppl 2*, E1-40.

doi:10.1097/01.hjr.0000277984.31558.c4 [doi]

Gutierrez-Rojas, L., Pulido, S., Azanza, J. R., Bernardo, M., Rojo, L., Mesa, F. J., & Martinez-Ortega, J. M. (2016). Risk factor assessment and counselling for 12 months reduces metabolic and cardiovascular risk in overweight or obese patients with schizophrenia spectrum disorders: The CRESSOB study. *Actas Espanolas De Psiquiatria, 44*(1), 20-29.

Hamer, M., & Stamatakis, E. (2012). Metabolically healthy obesity and risk of all-cause and cardiovascular disease mortality. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology and Metabolism, 97*(7), 2482-2488. doi:10.1210/jc.2011-3475 [doi]

- Hill, A. V., & Hartley Lupton, H. (1923). Muscular exercise, lactic acid, and the supply and utilization of oxygen. *An International Journal of Medicine*, *16*(62), 135-171.
- Huang, J., Hei, G. R., Yang, Y., Liu, C. C., Xiao, J. M., Long, Y. J., . . . Wu, R. R. (2020). Increased appetite plays a key role in olanzapine-induced weight gain in first-episode schizophrenia patients. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, *11*, 739. doi:10.3389/fphar.2020.00739 [doi]
- Huang, T. L., & Chen, J. F. (2005). Serum lipid profiles and schizophrenia: Effects of conventional or atypical antipsychotic drugs in taiwan. *Schizophrenia Research*, *80*(1), 55-59. doi:S0920-9964(05)00191-X [pii]
- Iwamoto, Y., Kawanishi, C., Kishida, I., Furuno, T., Fujibayashi, M., Ishii, C., . . . Hirayasu, Y. (2012a). Dose-dependent effect of antipsychotic drugs on autonomic nervous system activity in schizophrenia. *BMC Psychiatry*, *12*, 199-244X-12-199. doi:10.1186/1471-244X-12-199 [doi]
- Iwamoto, Y., Kawanishi, C., Kishida, I., Furuno, T., Fujibayashi, M., Ishii, C., . . . Hirayasu, Y. (2012b). Dose-dependent effect of antipsychotic drugs on autonomic nervous system activity in schizophrenia. *BMC Psychiatry*, *12*, 199-244X-12-199. doi:10.1186/1471-244X-12-199 [doi]
- Johnson, R. J. (2015). Why focus on uric acid? *Current Medical Research and Opinion*, *31* Suppl 2, 3-7. doi:10.1185/03007995.2015.1087979 [doi]
- Kaminsky, L. A., Arena, R., Ellingsen, O., Harber, M. P., Myers, J., Ozemek, C., & Ross, R. (2019). Cardiorespiratory fitness and cardiovascular disease - the past, present, and future. *Progress in Cardiovascular Diseases*, *62*(2), 86-93. doi:S0033-0620(19)30002-7 [pii]
- Kaminsky, L. A., Imboden, M. T., Arena, R., & Myers, J. (2017). Reference standards for cardiorespiratory fitness measured with cardiopulmonary exercise testing using cycle

ergometry: Data from the fitness registry and the importance of exercise national database (FRIEND) registry. *Mayo Clinic Proceedings*, 92(2), 228-233. doi:S0025-6196(16)30624-3 [pii]

Lang, R. M., Badano, L. P., Mor-Avi, V., Afilalo, J., Armstrong, A., Ernande, L., . . . Voigt, J. U. (2015). Recommendations for cardiac chamber quantification by echocardiography in adults: An update from the american society of echocardiography and the european association of cardiovascular imaging. *Journal of the American Society of Echocardiography : Official Publication of the American Society of Echocardiography*, 28(1), 1-39.e14. doi:10.1016/j.echo.2014.10.003 [doi]

Laursen, T. M., Munk-Olsen, T., & Vestergaard, M. (2012). Life expectancy and cardiovascular mortality in persons with schizophrenia. *Current Opinion in Psychiatry*, 25(2), 83-88. doi:10.1097/YCO.0b013e32835035ca [doi]

Lieberman, J. A., & First, M. B. (2018). Psychotic disorders. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 379(3), 270-80.

Lieberman, J. A., Stroup, T. S., & Perkins, D. O. (Eds.). (2006). *The american psychiatric publishing textbook of schizophrenia*. Arlington, VA, US: American Psychiatric Publishing.

Lis, M., Stanczykiewicz, B., Liskiewicz, P., & Misiak, B. (2020). Impaired hormonal regulation of appetite in schizophrenia: A narrative review dissecting intrinsic mechanisms and the effects of antipsychotics. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, 119, 104744. doi:S0306-4530(20)30163-3 [pii]

Maayan, L., Vakhrusheva, J., & Correll, C. U. (2010). Effectiveness of medications used to attenuate antipsychotic-related weight gain and metabolic abnormalities: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Neuropsychopharmacology : Official Publication of the*

American College of Neuropsychopharmacology, 35(7), 1520-1530.

doi:10.1038/npp.2010.21 [doi]

Mackin, P., Bishop, D. R., & Watkinson, H. M. (2007). A prospective study of monitoring practices for metabolic disease in antipsychotic-treated community psychiatric patients.

BMC Psychiatry, 7, 28-244X-7-28. doi:1471-244X-7-28 [pii]

Martinez-Larrad, M. T., Corbaton Anchuelo, A., Del Prado, N., Ibarra Rueda, J. M., Gabriel, R., & Serrano-Rios, M. (2014). Profile of individuals who are metabolically healthy obese using different definition criteria. A population-based analysis in the spanish population.

PloS One, 9(9), e106641. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0106641 [doi]

Matthews, D. R., Hosker, J. P., Rudenski, A. S., Naylor, B. A., Treacher, D. F., & Turner, R. C. (1985). Homeostasis model assessment: Insulin resistance and beta-cell function from fasting plasma glucose and insulin concentrations in man. *Diabetologia*, 28(7), 412-419.

doi:10.1007/bf00280883 [doi]

McHugh, M. L. (2013). The chi-square test of independence. *Biochemia Medica*, 23(2), 143-149.

Mezzani, A., Hamm, L. F., Jones, A. M., McBride, P. E., Moholdt, T., Stone, J. A., . . .

Canadian Association of Cardiac Rehabilitation. (2012). Aerobic exercise intensity assessment and prescription in cardiac rehabilitation: A joint position statement of the european association for cardiovascular prevention and rehabilitation, the american association of cardiovascular and pulmonary rehabilitation, and the canadian association of cardiac rehabilitation. *Journal of Cardiopulmonary Rehabilitation and Prevention*, 32(6), 327-350. doi:10.1097/HCR.0b013e3182757050 [doi]

- Montaquila, J. M., Trachik, B. J., & Bedwell, J. S. (2015). Heart rate variability and vagal tone in schizophrenia: A review. *Journal of Psychiatric Research, 69*, 57-66.
doi:10.1016/j.jpsychires.2015.07.025 [doi]
- Mukundan, A., Faulkner, G., Cohn, T., & Remington, G. (2010). Antipsychotic switching for people with schizophrenia who have neuroleptic-induced weight or metabolic problems. *The Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews, (12):CD006629*. doi(12), CD006629.
doi:10.1002/14651858.CD006629.pub2 [doi]
- Nagano, M., Sasaki, H., & Kumagai, S. (2010). Association of cardiorespiratory fitness with elevated hepatic enzyme and liver fat in Japanese patients with impaired glucose tolerance and type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Journal of Sports Science & Medicine, 9*(3), 405-410.
- National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP) Expert Panel on Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Cholesterol in Adults (Adult Treatment Panel III). (Circulation 2002). Third report of the national cholesterol education program (NCEP) expert panel on detection, evaluation, and treatment of high blood cholesterol in adults (adult treatment panel III) final report. *106*, 3143-21.
- National Collaborating Centre for Mental Health (UK). (2009). Schizophrenia: Core interventions in the treatment and management of schizophrenia in primary and secondary care (update) [internet]. *British Psychological Society*, doi:NBK11681 [bookaccession]
- Ohayon, M., Wickwire, E. M., Hirshkowitz, M., Albert, S. M., Avidan, A., Daly, F. J., . . . Vitiello, M. V. (2017). National sleep foundation's sleep quality recommendations: First report. *Sleep Health, 3*(1), 6-19. doi:S2352-7218(16)30130-9 [pii]
- Olfson, M., Gerhard, T., Huang, C., Crystal, S., & Stroup, T. S. (2015). Premature mortality among adults with schizophrenia in the United States. *JAMA Psychiatry, 72*(12), 1172-1181. doi:10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2015.1737 [doi]

Parks, K. A., Parks, C. G., Yost, J. P., Bennett, J. I., & Onwuameze, O. E. (2018). Acute blood pressure changes associated with antipsychotic administration to psychiatric inpatients. *The Primary Care Companion for CNS Disorders*, 20(4), 10.4088/PCC.18m02299. doi:10.4088/PCC.18m02299 [doi]

Piepoli, M. F., Hoes, A. W., Agewall, S., Albus, C., Brotons, C., Catapano, A. L., . . . Verschuren, W. M. M. (2017). 2016 european guidelines on cardiovascular disease prevention in clinical practice. the sixth joint task force of the european society of cardiology and other societies on cardiovascular disease prevention in clinical practice (constituted by representatives of 10 societies and by invited experts. developed with the special contribution of the european association for cardiovascular prevention & rehabilitation. [Linee guida europee 2016 sulla prevenzione delle malattie cardiovascolari nella pratica clinica. Sesta Task Force congiunta della Societa Europea di Cardiologia e di altre Societa sulla Prevenzione delle Malattie Cardiovascolari nella Pratica Clinica (costituita da rappresentanti di 10 societa e da esperti invitati). Redatte con il contributo straordinario dell'Associazione Europea per la Prevenzione e Riabilitazione Cardiovascolare (EACPR)] *Giornale Italiano Di Cardiologia* (2006), 18(7), 547-612. doi:10.1714/2729.27821 [doi]

Ramos, P. S., & Araujo, C. G. (2017). Cardiorespiratory optimal point during exercise testing as a predictor of all-cause mortality. *Revista Portuguesa De Cardiologia : Orgao Oficial Da Sociedade Portuguesa De Cardiologia = Portuguese Journal of Cardiology : An Official Journal of the Portuguese Society of Cardiology*, 36(4), 261-269. doi:S0870-2551(17)30139-7 [pii]

Ramos, P. S., Ricardo, D. R., & Araujo, C. G. (2012). Cardiorespiratory optimal point: A submaximal variable of the cardiopulmonary exercise testing. *Arquivos Brasileiros De Cardiologia*, 99(5), 988-996. doi:S0066-782X2012005000091 [pii]

Ratliff, J. C., Palmese, L. B., Reutenauer, E. L., Liskov, E., Grilo, C. M., & Tek, C. (2012). The effect of dietary and physical activity pattern on metabolic profile in individuals with schizophrenia: A cross-sectional study. *Comprehensive Psychiatry*, *53*(7), 1028-1033. doi:10.1016/j.comppsy.2012.02.003 [doi]

Saiz Ruiz, J., Bobes Garcia, J., Vallejo Ruiloba, J., Giner Ubago, J., Garcia-Portilla Gonzalez, M. P., & Grupo de Trabajo sobre la Salud Fisica del Paciente con Esquizofrenia. (2008). Consensus on physical health of patients with schizophrenia from the spanish societies of psychiatry and biological psychiatry. [Consenso sobre la salud fisica del paciente con esquizofrenia de las Sociedades Espanolas de Psiquiatria y de Psiquiatria Biologica] *Actas Espanolas De Psiquiatria*, *36*(5), 251-264. doi:20081110512 [pii]

Scheewe, T. W., Takken, T., Kahn, R. S., Cahn, W., & Backx, F. J. (2012). Effects of exercise therapy on cardiorespiratory fitness in patients with schizophrenia. *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, *44*(10), 1834-1842. doi:10.1249/MSS.0b013e318258e120 [doi]

Schutte-Rodin, S., Broch, L., Buysse, D., Dorsey, C., & Sateia, M. (2008). Clinical guideline for the evaluation and management of chronic insomnia in adults. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine : JCSM : Official Publication of the American Academy of Sleep Medicine*, *4*(5), 487-504.

Stubbs, B., Firth, J., Berry, A., Schuch, F. B., Rosenbaum, S., Gaughran, F., . . . Vancampfort, D. (2016). How much physical activity do people with schizophrenia engage in? A systematic review, comparative meta-analysis and meta-regression. *Schizophrenia Research*, *176*(2-3), 431-440. doi:S0920-9964(16)30241-9 [pii]

Tandon, R., Lenderking, W. R., Weiss, C., Shalhoub, H., Barbosa, C. D., Chen, J., . . . Castle, D. (2020). The impact on functioning of second-generation antipsychotic medication side effects for patients with schizophrenia: A worldwide, cross-sectional, web-based survey.

Annals of General Psychiatry, 19, 42-020-00292-5. eCollection 2020. doi:10.1186/s12991-020-00292-5 [doi]

Taxis, K., Schorr, S., Fouchier, M., Slooff, C., & Bruggeman, R. (2008). Is it appropriate to use cardiovascular risk scores in patients with psychotic disorders? *Schizophrenia Research*, 102(1-3), 169.

Tumiel, E., Wichniak, A., Jarema, M., & Lew-Starowicz, M. (2019). Nonpharmacological interventions for the treatment of cardiometabolic risk factors in people with schizophrenia-A systematic review. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 10, 566. doi:10.3389/fpsy.2019.00566 [doi]

Volpe, M., Gallo, G., Battistoni, A., & Tocci, G. (2019). Highlights of ESC/ESH 2018 guidelines on the management of hypertension: What every doctor should know. *High Blood Pressure & Cardiovascular Prevention : The Official Journal of the Italian Society of Hypertension*, 26(1), 1-8. doi:10.1007/s40292-018-00297-y [doi]

Watson, N., Badr, M., Belenky, G., Bliwise, D., Buxton, O., Buysse, D., . . . Tasali, E. (2015). Joint consensus statement of the american Academy of sleep medicine and sleep research society on the recommended amount of sleep for a healthy adult: Methodology and Discussion Amount of sleep for a healthy adult: Methodology and discussion. *Sleep*, 38(8), 1161-83.

Figure 1. Comparison of cardiovascular risk estimation in the studied groups.

SCORE: Systematic Coronary Risk Estimation

RELATIVE: Relative Risk

FHS: Framingham Heart Study.

* $P < 0.001$: Significant difference between CORTEX and HEALTHY

Figure 2. Comparison of vascular age (VA) and chronological age (CA) in the studied groups

* $P < 0.001$: Significant difference between CORTEX and HEALTHY.

Table 1. Characteristics of the studied populations.

Variables	CORTEX n=126	HEALTHY n=30	<i>P</i> CORTEX vs. HEALTHY	<i>d</i> Cohen/ Cramer's <i>V</i>
Age (yrs)	41.6±10.2	40.0±9.0	0.419	0.17
Body mass (kg)	83.7±16.2	66.1±10.5	<0.001***	1.29
BMI (kg/m²)	27.6±7.4	22.7±2.6	<0.001***	0.88
Waist (cm)	96.5±14.3	74.7±8.1	<0.001***	1.88
Hip (cm)	104.2±9.5	96.3±5.5	<0.001***	1.02
WHR	0.92±0.09	0.78±0.07	<0.001***	1.74
FFM (%)	73.5±10.4	78.5±10.3	<0.001***	0.48
TBW (%)	53.8±7.7	57.5±7.5	<0.001***	0.49
FBM (%)	26.5±10.4	21.5±10.4	<0.001***	0.48
SBP (mmHg)	115±13	113±10	0.505	0.17
DBP (mmHg)	70±8	68±7	0.070	0.37
Mean HR (bpm)	81±11	58±6	<0.001***	2.43
Cigarette smoking (%)	62.7	16.1	<0.001***	0.37
Diabetes Mellitus (%)	8.7	-	-	-
Antipsychotic treatment (%)	100	-	-	-
First-generation	2.4	-	-	-
Second-generation	93.6	-	-	-
Mixed	4.0	-	-	-
First-generation				
Haloperidol (%)	3.1	-	-	-
Levomepromazine (%)	3.1	-	-	-
Perphenazine (%)	0.8	-	-	-
Second-generation				
Aripiprazole (%)	20.3	-	-	-
Clozapine (%)	43.0	-	-	-
Lurasidone (%)	1.6	-	-	-
Olanzapine (%)	21.1	-	-	-
Paliperidone (%)	31.3	-	-	-
Quetiapine (%)	5.5	-	-	-
Risperidone (%)	7.0	-	-	-
Ziprasidone (%)	2.3	-	-	-
Concomitant medication				
Anticholinergics (%)	7.3	-	-	-
Antidepressants (%)	27.3	-	-	-
Benzodiazepines (%)	49.1	-	-	-
Mood stabilizers (%)	13.6	-	-	-

BMI, body mass index; WHR, waist to hip ratio; FFM, fat-free mass; TBW, total body water; FBM, fat body mass; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; HR, heart rate

P<0.05: Significant difference between CORTEX and HEALTHY

P*<0.05, ** *P*<0.01, * *P*<0.001

Table 2. Participants' exercise function.

Variables	CORTEX n=122	HEALTHY n=30	P_{CORTEX} vs. HEALTHY	d Cohen
Workload_{peak} (W)	126±54	233±76	<0.001***	1.62
Time (min)	10±6	18±7	<0.001***	1.22
Distance (km)	1.6±1.3	4.5±2.6	<0.001***	1.41
SBP_{peak} (mmHg)	183±29	185±26	0.784	0.06
DBP_{peak} (mmHg)	85±22	7±18	0.034*	0.40
HR_{peak} (bpm)	153±18	180±10	<0.001***	1.81
$\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ (L·min⁻¹)	1.8±0.8	3.1±1.1	<0.001***	1.35
$\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ (mL·kg⁻¹·min⁻¹)	22.5±9.0	50.0±12.0	<0.001***	2.59
$\dot{V}CO_{2peak}$ (L·min⁻¹)	2.2±1.0	3.4±1.4	<0.001***	0.99
RER_{peak}	1.2±0.1	1.1±0.1	0.607	1
MET_{peak}	6.4±2.7	14.2±3.2	<0.001***	2.63
VT₁ (mL·kg⁻¹·min⁻¹)	12.0±6.0	28.0±10.5	<0.001***	1.87
COP	30±6	25±4	<0.001***	1.21
MSWT (m)	795±390	1500±180	<0.001***	2.32

SBP_{peak}, peak systolic blood pressure; DBP_{peak}, peak diastolic blood pressure; HR_{peak}, peak heart rate; $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$, peak oxygen uptake; $\dot{V}CO_{2peak}$, peak carbon dioxide production; RER_{peak}, peak respiratory exchange ratio; MET_{peak}, peak metabolic equivalent of task; VT₁, first ventilatory threshold; COP, cardiorespiratory optimal point; MSWT, modified shuttle walking test distance.

$P < 0.05$: Significant difference between CORTEX and HEALTHY

* $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$

Table 3. Biochemical profile characteristics of the study's participants.

Variables	CORTEX n=125	HEALTHY n=30	<i>P</i> _{CORTEX vs. HEALTHY}	<i>d</i> Cohen
Hemoglobin (mg/dL)	14.8±1.3	14.3±0.9	0.039*	0.45
Hematocrit (%)	44.2±3.7	43.8±3.2	0.593	0.12
Glucose (mg/dL)	91.0±14.0	85.0±13.0	<0.001***	0.44
HOMA-IR	1.8±1.7	0.9±0.4	<0.001***	0.73
Insulin (μU/mL)	7.8±6.8	4.1±1.9	<0.001***	0.74
TC (mg/dL)	187.1±42.4	183.6±35.1	0.686	0.09
HDL-C (mg/dL)	40.0±15.0	63.0±17.0	<0.001***	1.43
LDL-C (mg/dL)	114.6±39.0	104.8±30.3	0.223	0.28
TC/HDL-C ratio	4.7±1.9	2.9±0.9	<0.001***	1.21
TG (mg/dL)	115.0±85.0	65.0±25.0	<0.001***	0.80
AST (U/L)	18.0±6.0	21.0±4.0	<0.001***	0.59
ALT (U/L)	21.5±14.0	18.0±9.0	0.010*	0.30
GGT (U/L)	20.0±14.0	14.0±7.0	<0.001***	0.54
Uric acid (mg/dL)	6.0±1.3	4.7±1.1	<0.001***	1.08
CRP (mg/L)	3.1±4.6	0.5±0.6	<0.001***	0.79

HOMA-IR, homeostasis model assessment of insulin resistance; TC, total cholesterol; HDL-C, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol; LDL-C, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol; TG, triglycerides; AST, aspartate transaminase; ALT, alanine transaminase; GGT, gamma-glutamyl transferase; CRP, C-reactive protein

P<0.05: Significant difference between CORTEX and HEALTHY

P*<0.05, *P*<0.01, ****P*<0.001.

Table 4. Sleep variables analysis of study population

Variables	CORTEX n=113	HEALTHY n=30	P_{CORTEX} vs. HEALTHY	d Cohen
Sleep Efficiency (%)	91.5±5.4	92.4±3.5	0.987	0.20
TST (min)	553.9±145.2	415.3±70.6	<0.001***	1.21
WASO (min)	49.6±28.0	32.9±13.1	0.004**	0.76

TST, total sleep time; WASO, wake after sleep onset.

$P < 0.05$: Significant difference between CORTEX and HEALTHY

* $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$